

Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Culture of Employees in Plastic Manufacturing Company

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Abstract: The study aimed to determine which domain in the human resource management practices best influences the organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company. The study employed quantitative non-experimental research utilizing correlational technique with 200 employees as test respondents in Macondray Plastics Products, Inc., Panabo area. Mean, Pearson r and Regression were the statistical tools used for the data treatment. Data were gathered in the human resources management practices and organizational culture through two adopted questionnaires. Results show a high level of human resource management practices and organizational culture. Further, the study revealed that human resource management practices are very high in terms of professional training, career management, and retention. A significant relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees was also established. Notably, when regressed, retention posted to have a significant influence on organizational culture, hence, considered to be the best predictor of organizational culture.

Keywords: career management, correlation research design, human resource management practices, organizational culture, Philippines, professional training, retention

I. Introduction

Organizational culture building is a long-way process and it takes remarkable time in getting to be established. Top management puts all effort to deliver the organizational culture to their employees in its real positive spirit. However, if the management fails to synchronize both formal and informal channels in the right mode, no management can deliver its culture in a productive manner. Organizations where, old employees do not fuse their informal channels with formal channels, their organizations may face some effects like confused environment, employee demoralization, increased employee turnover rate and lack of employee retainship (Thakur, 2010). An underpaid, overworked and undervalued employee may seek to quit and work abroad. Thus, top management is challenged in this demanding realm of work to build an organizational culture that enables them to retain their skilled employees, give them incentive and monitor the turnover rate of the employees. (Kalaw, 2014).

Due to its prospect of affecting a wide range of organizationally and personally desired outcomes such as engagement, loyalty, focus on turnover and satisfaction, organizational culture has been an important element in management and business research for the past few decades. It is also important that all managements should understand the role of old workers during organizational culture delivery process. Every part of the organization its building, products, suppliers, customers, traditions, old workers are potential culture delivery sources of its kind and management must understand the role of old employees because it is the most effective and active source of organizational culture delivery (Thakur, 2010).

A significant body of literature signifying that HRM practices and organizational culture are related. McAfee, Glassman, and Honeycutt (2002) denote to the culture and HRM practices relationship as symbiotic that it operates to communicate organizational values and beliefs. They also analyzed the effect of human resource management practices, organizational culture, organizational creativity and knowledge management on organizational efficiency, as posited by Al-bahussin and El-Garaihy (2013). The study population comprised 203 human resource directors employed in large organizations in Saudi Arabia's eastern region. Results showed that managing human resources is a significant antecedent of organizational culture, information management and creativity in the organization. The attraction of successful applicants in the recruitment process, for example, will also follow the organizational culture, and the organizational culture will influence the recruitment processes (Williams, 2014). Even, Madanat and Khasawneh (2018) exhibited an empirically proven relationship among HRM practices, organizational culture, and organizational outcomes.

Although several literature reviews have examined relationships between HRM practices and organizational culture across industries, their focus in plastic manufacturing was inadequate. Human resource management practices are established and recognized based on the management of organizational culture in the organization. It plays a vital role as supporting element of business strategy, which may offer the supreme and premier potential leverage for HR to improve an organization's financial performance. Organizational culture is one of several attributes that differentiate companies from one another and that these unrelenting and prolonged differences can explain sustained superior financial performance. Although, the relationship of HRM practices and activities, organizational cultures, and organizational results has been tested in the general business literature that these links in health care organizations and not in plastic manufacturing industry (Platonova, 2005).

This study therefore, contributes to the literature on human resources management practices and organizational culture as it intends to determine which domain in the human resource management practices significantly influences the organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company. This will serve as a catalyst to encourage business owners, HR Managers, and HR practitioners of plastic manufacturing companies that human resource management practices and organizational culture in the organization are essential in the business to boost organizational economic growth. Human Resource Management as a function and as a prime mover would need to focus on this changing and emerging role to help the organization.

1.1 Research Objective

This research paper aims to determine which domain in the human resource management practices best influences the organizational culture. It sought to reply to the following objectives, for the purpose:

1.1.1 To describe the level of human resource management practices in terms of:

- 1.1.1.1 professional training;
- 1.1.1.2 career management; and
- 1.1.1.3 retention.

1.1.2 To determine the level of organizational culture in terms of:

- 1.1.2.1 clan culture;
- 1.1.2.2 adhocracy culture;
- 1.1.2.3 market culture; and
- 1.1.2.4 hierarchy culture.

1.1.3 To establish the significance of the relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture.

1.1.4 To identify which domain of human resource management practices best influences the organizational culture.

1.2 Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1.2.1 There is no significant relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company.

1.2.2 There is no domain in the human resource management practices that best influences the organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company.

1.3 Review of Related Literature

The literature review in this chapter includes human resource management practices particularly related to career management, professional training perspectives, and retention (Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, & Mónico, 2014). Though organizational culture primarily includes the tribe, adhocracy, market and hierarchy. The six subscales of each type of organizational culture include dominant purpose, organizational glue, strategic emphasis and performance criteria (Jones, 2009).

1.3.1 Human Resource Management Practices

Human resource management practices specifically related to career management, professional training perspectives and retention (Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, and Mónico, 2014). HRM activities are seen as a set of practices that the company uses in managing human resources to promote the development of firm-specific skills, generate multifaceted social relationships, and generate awareness of organizations to sustain competitive advantage. The author concluded that HRM activities align with specific practices, structured strategies, and philosophies aimed at attracting, creating, empowering, and retaining workers who safeguard the organization's successful functioning and survival (Jiménez & Valle, 2013).

As studied by Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, and Mónico (2014), they describe HRM best practices as a collection of the organization's entire HRM practices and policies that provide guidance for a successful improvement in organizational efficiency. In their opinion, the most sound and effective activities are the high level of group work, smart recruiting and selection processes, minimal status gaps, extensive training, protocols and agreement for internal communication and employee engagement, in-house career opportunities, and standardized explanation of roles are very little. It meant valuing the talents, skills and knowledge of employees through successful recruitment and training, empowering them from a strong incentive system, and fostering opportunities for the most highly qualified and motivated workers, influencing the expansion of their knowledge and skills through streamlining work and indirect forms of engagement. Professional training is the organization's intended attempts to speed up the learning of job-related skills by employees. Those skills integrate expertise, skills, or attitudes essential for successful job results. Learning and development help to improve human resource efficiency that further helps the employee meet the corporate objectives as well as their individual goals. It also helps foster and restore the organizational culture within the company by building the organization's positive experiences and feelings (Osibanjo, Adeniji, & Abiodun, 2013). They pronounce with this interpretation, as viewed by Jiménez and Valle (2013), when they note that the literature distinguishes the two basic perspectives that organizations should take about the management of relationships with their employees. They differentiate between a transactional or conventional perspective that dictates the theory of HRM practices that promote short-term exchange relationships between the company and its workers, and another one based on high-involvement HRM practices that prioritize long-term reciprocal exchange ties. Nonetheless, they state they typically involve creating opportunities for internal market growth and promotion, recruiting and selection based more on alignment between candidates and the company than on specific function, evaluation and incentive systems criteria, training and development activities that facilitate long-term employee development and teambuilding. A research paper by Mohamed and Leponiemi (2009) affirmed that employee views about the professional training for career development they obtain from their organizations will influence their commitment. The results suggest that feelings of responsibility to the organization are simply governed by opportunities for development and a general acceptance of the organization's culture. This provides support to the concept that some type of reciprocity and trustworthiness in return for reward opportunities in other organizations.

Correspondingly, employees give importance on professional training as a resource for self-improvement, and a resource that could be remarked as a loss of departing the organization. Career workshop and professional training would help employees to be promoted within the organization, increase their desire to grow and learn, and to support them by providing opportunities for lateral movement to boost their morale. Through these training employees would be able to adapt easily when necessary. Employees will develop skills and abilities, enhance their knowledge, improve

their self-efficacy, self-improvement, and lessen their need for supervision. By doing these, employees would feel important and respected that this would contribute to their retention to the organization (Palmer, 2006).

Apart from the conventional way of attracting, educating, keeping and empowering staff, human resource management (HRM) activities will improve and promote a good learning culture where there is an open transfer of information on the job. As researched by Arunprasad (2016), they endeavored to research the different HR policies in order to create a safer environment for an organization with "intensive expertise" to retain and continue their senior talent within the company. Specialized training programs such as success management, company experience, collaboration and the development of integrated teams and maximize individual learning opportunities. This is in line with the analysis of Battistuzzo, Callister, Callister, and Galea (2012) which provides a solid foundation for employees to gather and share new information through distinctive training. Job rotations, mentoring and coaching development in the organizations fortify the talent pipeline and support their potential development as observed that there are similar empirical evidence in the study of Arunprasad (2016). Those individuals who aspire to career growth will possess certain characteristics of the transformer strategy such as openness, strategic thinking, imagination, personal effectiveness and empathy are emphasized in individuals through long-term rewards for creative thinking, individual and community opportunities for knowledge exchange and information sharing, competency- and performance-based compensation, profit sharing.

It reaffirms the research carried out by Jiménez and Valle (2013) on aspects aimed at employee learning and knowledge transfer within the company through performance evaluation, career management, and training programmes. Concerning training, several studies feature the positive effect of professional training on knowledge management because it plays an important role in preserving and developing individual capabilities and a learning-oriented organizational culture. More recent empirical studies of HRM practices by Peter and Eunice (2014) revealed six underlying business performance HRM practices, including training and growth, collaboration, rewards and benefits, HR preparation, performance management and employee protection, helping to improve the business performance of firms including employee engagement, product quality and flexibility. This research reveals that three elements of HRM practices affect business performance, professional development and training, rewards and benefits, and HR preparation. In order to simplify the efficacy of Arunprasad's seven HRM practices (2016), the seven HRM practices have been discovered, such as job security, selective recruiting, team use and decentralization, performance-related rewards and reward based, extensive training, status gap and information sharing. HRM activities including professional training and development, teamwork, compensation, human resource planning, and performance evaluation have a significant impact on employee engagement in their report. As Peter and Eunice (2014) put it, he introduced eleven HRM practices, recognizing that workplace safety, team work and incentive incentives are perceived to be three of the key activities that affect hospital results.

Practices in human resource management (HRM) are recognized internationally as playing a critical role in creating and maintaining organizational success. Organizations manage human resources through the establishment of departments for human resources (HR) in a functional organizational structure, although HR's position is not confined to the departments themselves. A large number of experts in the region warn that HRM faces survival unless it reacts to changes brought about by the transition from a conventional economy to a knowledge-based one. It is therefore imperative to choose appropriate HRM practices which promote the sharing of knowledge in a particular organization. Many HRM activities are found to be useful in promoting conduct of knowledge sharing, such as recruitment and selection, compensation and reward, performance evaluation, collaboration, professional training and development (Rana &Goel, 2012).

Such HRM activities ultimately improve organizational involvement, inspire workers and generally influence the ability of employees to develop, communicate or discover information across the company (Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, &Mónico, 2014). The findings have indicated that human resources management practices such as reward strategy, career management and recruitment strategy directs to knowledge management culture in organization. It can be defined that incentive policy, career-oriented training and recruitment strategy related to the fulfillment of cognitive needs such as employees' learning, development and decision making, as well as influencing their job efficiency and results as necessary. Consequently, human resource management practices effectively provide a conducive platform for developing and creating new training as well as information acquisition, sharing and distribution in the organization which support to perform employee's activities and developing further potential for managing sustainable competitive advantage. Successful recruitment strategy and career management programme at workplace widen employees

competency, knowledge, learning and increase latitude in decision making which further produce the feelings of being accepted, unrelenting growth and overall work fulfillment.

It has been hypothesized by Arunprasad (2016) that HRM activities are a series of internally consistent policies and practices designed and applied to warrant that the human capital of an organization interposes with the achievement of its business goals. Similarly, Nasurdin, Ling, and Fun (2011) described HRM practices as an individual's understanding of the degree to which the tactics, plans and initiatives used to attract, inspire, grow, reward and retain the best staff to meet organizational expectations is implemented. Based on the arguments put forward by these authors, HRM strategies include specific practices, structured policies, and philosophies designed to attract, grow, empower and retain employees who guarantee the organization's organizational functioning and survival.

HRM, on the other hand, is the premeditated and logical approach to managing the most important assets of a company and matches them with the strategic business requirements. It is acknowledged that competitive advantage can be achieved with a skilled workforce which enables organizations to compete and succeed in business. Management of human resources has turned out to be more important to general management because of its role in enriching performance, attracting and improving employee talent and fostering collaboration between employees in support of organizational advancement. As mentioned, HRM is a process that focuses on securing and growing the skills of individual employees and strengthens communication and cooperation between them in order to stimulate the growth of organizations. HRM activities have an affirmative impact on organizational creativity, business strategy realization, work performance, financial returns, organizational conflict management and a viable competitive advantage. The most important aspects of HRM, all-encompassing work design, collaboration, hiring, preparation, career management, performance evaluation, and compensation, have been charted. Recruitment and selection strategies are premeditated to identify potential applicants for current and future work, and to produce appropriate choices. The active work climate and multifaceted market demands of today require employees to be skilled in conducting multiple tasks in an efficient and effective manner to create good career management for their employees. A well-ordered system of training and development provides continuous knowledge and experience to the employees. Education and development are eminent for expanding job performance, enriching productivity and happiness of workers, loosening costs and generating work value. It meant that training and development were constant efforts aimed at improving employee capacity and organizational performance by providing employees with the knowledge and skills needed to carry out their work.

As demonstrated by the metrics for successful HRM activities, the results include employee satisfaction, employee motivation, employee protection, employee assurance and employee allegiance. The company should therefore create a work environment that leads to the happiness, engagement and motivation of employees. It was argued that managers at the organizational level should be able to describe appropriate HRM strategies to help the company boost customer satisfaction and achieve competitive advantages. Efficiency and efficacy of HRMS have been evaluated in terms of human resource planning, selection and deployment, staff performance assessment, employee training and the relationship between these approaches and organizational performance.

Efficiency and efficacy of HRMS is evaluated in terms of human resource planning, selection and implementation, performance evaluation of personnel, training of employees and the relationship between these strategies and organizational efficiency. Career management was found to be the most substantial prerequisite of managerial effectiveness in shared sector organizations and it has a direct bearing on managerial deficiency. It also employs into consideration the individual performance evaluation, development, transfer and promotion in career management. Wide-ranging training extends the knowledge and abilities of staff and thus extend the workplace opportunities (Madanat&Khasawneh, 2018). This denotes training as strategies that are harnessed to provide the skills needed for the new recruits to perform their duties and responsibilities. Education has been discussed as the mechanism for promoting knowledge and skills as a way of boosting the success of individuals. They developed that career management has positive effects on the performance of the company and the employee. Employees may be provided in multiple functions and job skills training through specific training programs. Work excellence is high and organizational costs are low which train employees in multiple roles. In addition, training in multiple functions provides contextual consistency between groups, departments and employment and companies can affect more successful results and make employees more knowledgeable (Arunprasad, 2016).

Career management is involved in providing opportunities for people to develop and build jobs, and ensuring that the company has the talent pool it wants. The essential elements of career management are learning and development opportunities preparation, career planning, and succession planning management. Organizations are struggling with the employee retention problem due to increased market competition. Organizations need to recruit competent employees to gain a competitive advantage in the marketplace. The organization has employed various human resource strategies to improve the retention rates (Wickramasinghe&Jayaweera, 2010).

Organizations deal with employee turnover in monetary terms alone may not bear the cost of this situation. When we follow the constant overall workload, the short time pressure on the remaining employees will increase and have an adverse impact on their motivation. In the long-term the company lacks the seasoned workers who gain accurate knowledge, know-how and skills. In turn, new employee participation is combined with additional expenses. Such costs are incurred in the form of advertising, screening, checking interview qualifications and training of new employees etc. Employee retention requires processes through which workers are allowed to remain for a longer period of time as part of the organization until they are terminated or until the project is completed. To achieve individual as well as organizational goals, keeping talented employees is very critical. The HR manager should be able to entice and retain good workers because these are the employees who can build and destroy the trust of the company. Successful retention of staff is not based on a single strategy. An employee's decision to remain in the company is caused by a number of components depending on a variety of factors such as the age of the worker, the family situation, mentoring, employment and learning opportunities, good benefits, networking and the external job market or job title (Al-Emadi, Schwabenland, & Wei, 2015).

When businesses want to keep their key employees, they have to pay serious attention to their capital spending on training and development. Training supports creating a desire among the employee to remain with the organization for a longer period of time. A vital part of organizational plans should be vocational training and career management programs.

Developing firms commonly makes use of training programs for their staff to achieve strategic goals. Similar to their non-growing rivals, they illustrate the growth of employees. Thus in that organizations, training and workforce development programs are quite common. It is also of the same assessment, which suggests concentrating more on policies and practices that lead to retention of employees. Organizational culture is an essential aspect that causes the employees to leave the organization. Managers need to respect the organizational culture, its various elements and try to find out how to enhance culture to attract more workers.

Employee retention is the willingness to retain the employee for a longer period of time within a company. Longevity of talent is important for businesses that move from start-up to fast growth. It is important to keep the best people closest to the core competencies of the organisation. Retaining workers is about circumventing the risk of turnover. Organization must maintain the people who execute and have skills and competencies that suit the core talent needs of the business (Haider, Rasli, Akhtar, Yusoff, Malik, Aamir, Arif, Naveed, & Tariq, 2015).

1.3.2 Organizational Culture

Specifically, organizational culture comprises the community, adhocracy, market and hierarchy. The six subscales of each type of organization included dominant characteristics, organizational leadership, employee management, organizational glue, strategic emphases and performance criteria. Organizational culture is a vague term, since there is no distinct concept generally accepted by each of the organizational culture literatures. The difficulty of giving a clear description of culture is to provide a concept of its behavior as well as its reactions.

The competing values framework is developed and it categorized organizations according to two dimensions. The definition describes four forms of organizational culture including the culture of tribe, adhocracy, business, and hierarchy. The clan culture is a type of organizational culture best described as a friendly, cozy environment where commitment, communication and development are the main values.

While, culture of adhocracy sets a dynamic, creative environment, creativity and agility are the key values. Although power emanates from person to individual, task team to task team depends on how the issue is dealt with. Organizations that have this philosophy try to produce creative results and learn new opportunities. The business

culture, on the other hand, promotes a result-oriented atmosphere that maintains the core values like productivity and objective achievement (Jones, 2009).

Nonetheless, the culture of hierarchy is hierarchical, and organized framework promotes efficiency and consistency as the key values. Organizational culture associates the workers with the ideals, traditions, stories, beliefs and principles of the company and integrates such ideas as action and behavioral set of standards in them. It is defined as a vibrant force within the company that is moving, engaging and responsive and is influenced by the workers and the actions, behaviors and attitudes of the management. It argues that culture starts with leadership and passes on to members of the organization that it is regarded as a collection of forces that shape and influence human behavior (Giberson, Resick, Dickson, Mitchelson, Randall, & Clark, 2009).

Each of the four factors surrounding organizational culture has three types of variables. Participation is therefore distinguished by indices such as empowerment, team alignment, capacity growth, core values continuity, teamwork and integration, consensus, organizational learning adaptability, customer attention, change and task formation, vision, priorities and objectives, and strategy (Denison & Nieminen, 2014).

As the author says, "organizational culture reflects the individual's personality is secret, yet a unifying theme provides context, direction, and mobilization" (DellaNeve, 2007). We professed that there is no unanimity on detailed description in accordance with culture that cannot be clarified in any way accurately or fully. Even though all the concepts are similar to the notion they express and lead us to describe organizational culture as beliefs and shared values that unify and integrate members of an organization under the cover of powerful behavioral norms and rules. It implies that the influence of globalization referring to organizational culture that nurtured the points that globalization has contributed to the rise of some weight-bearing organizational culture (Ahmadi, Salamzadeh, Daraei, & Akbari, 2012).

As characterizes the culture as a set of values, it directs views, understandings, and ways of thinking held by an organization's members and taught new members as being right. Four forms of society have been circumscribed here. While researchers mark these types by different names, the main idea is similar for each type. Types of culture are bureaucratic that strategic focus is internal and the organization is stable in relation to its environment. Second is adaptive or entrepreneurial that strategic focus is external and organization is flexible in relation to its environment. The third is on mission that strategic focus is external and organization is stable in relation to its environment. Lastly, the clan culture that the strategic focus is internal and organization is flexible in relation to its environment.

These mutual assumptions postulate the foundation upon which the group solves problems of internal integration and external adaption. This defines the concept of culture as the intangible structure that includes common values, perceptions, norms, and convictions that serve as standards for individual behavior in an organization and is tangibly represented in the form of verbal, behavioral, and visual representations by those involved.

As Huang (2003) stated, the corporate culture is the collective belief system that individuals within an organization have about their ability to compete on the marketplace and how they operate on those belief systems to deliver value-added services and products to the company's customers and benefit. As described by Kalaw (2014), organizational culture as comprising the organization's attitudes, perceptions, beliefs, and values, acquired through social learning, which regulates how individuals and groups within the organization communicate with each other and with parties outside the organization. Organizations with a strong culture seek to maintain the culture by choosing people who already share the culture and by socializing new members to embrace those norms and values.

Kim (2014) fostered clan culture denotes that applying the structure of competing values takes into account that the company is like an extended family that it is a very personal environment. In particular, transformational leaders in the public sector may create or shape their own clan culture in terms of organizational utility by, among others, stressing cooperation, unity, employee growth, engagement, loyalty, dedication, and morale. The impression in the company has family-like atmosphere, contemplates solidarity and feeling of oneness as significant, and working as a team as essential.

As perceived by Son (2016), clan culture is a shared perception of trust that will mediate the negative individual relationship, organizations apportion higher proportion of pay based on organizational performance, promoting information sharing, cooperation, and eventually likelihood of an emergence. It is characterized as the motivation for interpersonal relatedness is an important factor of the psychological well-being of the human being. Furthermore,

organizations with clan culture provide attention to employees by providing pleasant work experience that can intensify employees' collective organizational commitment which is an imperative antecedent of employee outcomes, such as turnover and job performance.

It has been elaborated by Washington (2013) that clan culture characterized an ideal climate for employing and enterprise electronic health records between three varied organizations. It highlighted cooperation, conventional values of a family-oriented community, compassion to its customer that reciprocated an affirmative performance within the organization. The clan culture's reciprocity was foreseen on shared goals, sensitivity of leadership behaviors and actions that fostered teamwork, communication, and an open decision making practice. Employees need to understand organizational support for required resources, skills, and empowerment to accomplish organizational vision and goals (Washington, 2013).

Whereas, as posited by James-Parks (2015) the importance of adhocracy culture as an entrepreneurial organization that gives emphasis on creativity and innovation. Accountability to growth and revolution through experimentation and risk-taking is distinguished. Success is expressed by novel products and services. The organization encourages individual freedom and initiative.

As conceived by the authors, adhocracy culture emphasizes high flexibility and external focus setting. This type of culture tenets innovativeness, malleability and entrepreneurship. Individuals who are successful in this setting are more concerned with being creative than with each time being successful (Song, Le, & Wang, 2016).

In line with the other reports, versatility, adaptability, creativity and risk-taking by both workers and leaders are principles of adhocracy culture style of organisation. That unifies the company is a dedication to innovation and to think differently. This aims to assist company organizations through the implementation and development of technology and new ways of doing things for better work processes (Beyene, 2011).

In addition, adhocracy culture instills values which emphasize an external and organic emphasis that tends to create a creative and dynamic workplace. Its core function is breaking through normal routines, finding resources, solving problems and getting results. Dominant indicators of the organizational culture's type of adhocracy include entrepreneurship, innovation, creativity, risk-taking and adaptability (Wei, Samiee, & Lee, 2014)

While the market culture type of organization focuses on external maintenance and transactions. Such result-oriented organizations are led by leaders who are hard-driving, competitive and demanding. It is rational and objective-oriented, stressing maximum output, being effective and having guidance. It prides itself on success, development, profit-making or impact-making, logical production, external engagement and goal-making are the most important factors for the business culture. Members have a straightforward direction and are financially remunerated for their achievement (Harinarain, Bornman, & Botha, 2013).

Business culture, on the other hand, concentrates on its relationship with manufacturers, consumers and regulators and is more outwardly focused. This market cultural environment focuses on repository where employees were rewarded for involvements. It pronounces this type of organization as one that operates with a high degree of steadiness and control, focuses on external maintenance, and is vigilant in taking robust business initiatives (Ballaro & Washington, 2016).

In addition, business culture is a result-oriented atmosphere that focuses on targets and offers competitive advantage. Profitability, sustainability, efficiency, and objective accomplishment are the core principles that control business organizations. This culture has a competitive mindset, focusing on achieving the goals, and its market share and penetration determine its success. (Štemberger, Buh, Glavan, & Mendling, 2018).

As a result of the study of Yazici (2011), the authoritarian structure does not contribute substantially to project success and company performance. Because of its outcomes and focus towards development, consumer culture is supposed to contribute to external business performance. Competitiveness is achieved through a strong focus on the external positioning and strength. Performance is characterized in terms of market share and penetration, where the members have a high regard for authority, compliance, order, consistency and rigor (Yazici, 2011).

Concomitantly, when an organization has a new stimulus, which is not covered by existing policies and procedures, the hierarchical culture type of organization, these organizations have difficulties in deciding the best course of action. Standardized procedures ensure quality and reliable service that the public has come to expect and implement these procedures are many management levels to train workers to ensure compliance with the processes. In familiar settings, hierarchical organizations are effective and efficient, allowing members to implement standard policies and procedures. Nevertheless, these same companies do not adapt well to change and there is a lack of innovation, and it is difficult to solve unique problems due to the lack of an established mechanism for dealing with new problems that require a paradigm shift (Schimmoeller, 2007).

In addition, hierarchy culture is a highly formalized and organized organization where predictability and productivity depend on performance. Employees work on the basis of well-defined processes and members serve as coordinators. Instead of generating or exploiting new opportunities, the focus is on doing more of what they do well and increasing efficiency (Nukic&Huemann, 2016).

Eventually, organizational culture has been described as a set of beliefs, behaviors, behavioral norms, and values that are common to all of an organization's employees. Due to its prospect of affecting a wide range of organizationally and personally desired outcomes such as engagement, loyalty, turnover intent, and satisfaction, organizational culture has been an important element in management and business research for the past few decades (Isopeskul, Shakina, & Georgieva, 2016).

1.3.3 Correlation between Measures

First, as mentioned in the above literatures, organizations can use Human Resource Management practices to acquire and motivate employees with learning acquisition and transfer of knowledge. Several empirical researches postulate support for the affirmation that HR practices are related to organizational culture. Platonova (2005) used a quantitative approach to empirically demonstrate the connection between organizational culture, HRM procedures, and performance of the organizations. Reference was made to a comprehensive database of U.S. companies from a wide range of industries and sizes. Madanat and Khasawneh (2018) exhibited an empirically proven relationship among HRM practices, organizational culture, and organizational outcomes.

As postulated by Upadhyaya (2014), each organization should operate and strive to create its own unique culture, instead of replicating and imitating the culture of another organization by applying the hierarchy of needs theory correctly as suggested by Maslow. It is necessary to pick, amalgamate and integrate the right cultural elements over time to achieve and understand the unique requirements of one's organization, which necessitates the first stage in the hierarchy pyramid. It is in this hypothesis that there is a connection between organizational culture and HRM practices that some leaders applaud a certain culture, but yet when this comes to rewards, workers who follow the celebrated culture are not rewarded for their contributions, simply because there is no system in place for the HRM role of the company.

They researched the effect on organizational success of human resource management practices, organizational culture, organizational creativity and information management as posited by Al-bahussinand El-Garaihy (2013). The study population comprised 203 human resources directors working in large organizations in Saudi Arabia's eastern region. Results showed that managing human resources is a significant antecedent of organizational culture, information management and creativity in the organization. Human resources alignment with the organizational culture is a critical tool for the organization in achieving its objectives and producing results. Organizational culture can encourage its employees to join forces or engage in teamwork for change and improvement (Smith, Rohr, & Panton, 2018). Organizational culture support and HR strategy lead to shaping factors such as entering success, efficiency, and whether human capital will ultimately be a core competency (Harrison & Bazy, 2017). Human resource management has a strong influence on the organizational culture in an enterprise which is an integrated strategic human resource management model. For example, the attractiveness of talented applicants will follow the organizational culture in the recruitment process, and the organizational culture will influence the recruitment processes (Williams, 2014).

An extraordinary finding in this research is that there is a positive relationship between HRM activities and the culture of organization. In fact, almost all HRM practices appear to align with aspects of the organizational culture. Earlier research into the relationship between organizational culture and HRM activities requires this relationship. As mentioned, organizational culture has an important effect on internal recruiting, selection, compensation system, and performance evaluation. This organizational culture has influence on HR activities and their efficacy according to them.

To HR administrators this result has significant connections. We will employ the positive effects of organizational culture on these tasks to effective HRM operations. A significant body of literature signifying that HRM practices and organizational culture are related and symbiotic in nature. McAfee, Glassman, and Honeycutt (2002) denote to the culture and HRM practices relationship as symbiotic that it operates to communicate organizational values and beliefs. As discussed by Madanat and Khasawneh (2018), how the efficacy of HRM strategies on employee satisfaction, pay equity, role design through training and successful performance management impact the retention decision of workers, engagement and organizational culture.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

This study is based on several empirical investigations which validate the relationship between HR practices and organizational culture. This study is clearly anchored as postulated by Upadhyaya (2014), every organization should function and attempt to establish its own unique culture, rather than replicating and imitating the culture of another organization by correctly applying the hierarchy of the theory of needs as suggested by Maslow. It is necessary to pick, amalgamate and integrate the right cultural elements over time to achieve and understand the unique requirements of one's organization, which necessitates the first stage in the hierarchy pyramid. It is in this hypothesis that there is a connection between organizational culture and HRM practices that some leaders applaud a certain culture, but yet when this comes to rewards, workers who follow the celebrated culture are not rewarded for their contributions, simply because there is no system in place for the HRM role of the organization. As an alternative, organizations should consciously and intentionally map key cultural elements to their HRM role to encourage workers to engage in the culture embraced and endorsed by the management. This can be successfully achieved by tailoring and updating an established on - the-market HR program that reflects and represents the social needs.

This study is explicitly affixed in the idea of Platonova (2005) that HRM practices is connected with organizational culture and performance. A proposition that supports the association between HRM practices and organizational culture that has exhibited an empirically proven relationship among HRM practices, organizational culture, and organizational results.

In a study by Al-Bahussin and El-Garaihy (2013), among 203 human resource directors employed in large organizations in the eastern region of Saudi Arabia, they discovered that human resource management is a significant antecedent of organizational culture, information management and creativity.

1.5 Conceptual Framework

A model in Figure 1, shows the direct causal connection between the human resources management practices and the workers' organizational culture of plastic manufacturing company. The human resource management practices are specially related to career management, professional training, and retention (Haider et. al., 2015). Professional training has positive effects on the success of the employee, career selection offering opportunities for people to make progress in building their careers, and ensuring employee retention by keeping the best employees closest to the core competencies of the organization. The organizational culture framework developed by Jones (2009) presents organizational culture as clan culture that best describes as friendly and cozy environment, adhocracy culture that sets a dynamic and creative environment, market culture that fosters a results-oriented environment, and hierarchy culture as efficiency and stability are the formal and organized environment which drives the core values.

Fig.1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

1.6 Significance of the Study

This research adds to the body of knowledge on how to assess which area of human resource management practices is significantly affecting the plastic manufacturing company organizational culture. This will serve as a catalyst to encourage business owners, HR Managers, and HR practitioners of plastic manufacturing companies that human resource management practices and organizational culture in the organization are essential in the business to boost organizational economic growth. Human Resource Management as a function and as a prime mover would need to focus on this changing and emerging role to help the organization.

The findings of this study are of great help to the Human Resource Practitioners of the Philippine People Management Association in Davao Region, given that human resource management practices are organizational factors that play a vital role in the organization's organizational culture. Finally, this report acts as a tooling ground for researchers to apply their expertise and experiences to their future study and research on human resource management practices and organizational culture in other business sectors.

1.7 Definition of Terms

Following its use in this review, which includes human resource management practices and organizational culture, the words were defined:

Human Resource Management Practices refers to a set of practices that companies have embraced in managing human resources to promote the development of firm-specific skills, generate multifaceted social relationships, and generate awareness of organizations to preserve competitive advantage. The author concluded that HRM activities align with professional training, career selection, and unique procedures, structured strategies, and philosophies aimed at recruiting, creating, empowering, and maximizing employee retention to safeguard the organization's effective functioning and survival.

Organizational Culture includes the organization's attitudes, perceptions, beliefs and values, established through social learning, which influence the way individuals and groups within the organization communicate with each other and with outside parties. Organizations with a strong culture are trying to preserve the culture by choosing people who are already imparting the culture and combining new members to embrace those norms and values.

II. Method

The chapter addresses the approach used, research design, location, population and sample analysis, research instrument, data collection, statistical methods, and ethical concern used in the study.

2.1 Research Design

This research used quantitative, non-experimental designs and correlation techniques to determine the cause or factor affecting at least one variable in reaction to another variable to create the behavior. The design was conclusively determined the best fit model that establishes that causal relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees of plastic manufacturing company. The purpose of this study is to determine if a particular independent variable actually affects the dependent variable and, if any, estimate the magnitude of that influence (Allison, 2014).

Research Locale

The locale for the present study was located in Panabo City, Davao del Norte and the target respondents of this study are 206 employees in a plastic manufacturing company as enlisted in the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC). This plastic manufacturing company is mainly supplying banana plantation plastic bag requirements in the Davao Region, on the southern island of Mindanao. The company manufactures and markets varied polyolefin blown film products and polypropylene twine products which aim to become the leading supplier of quality plastic products and services to different target markets.

2.2 Population and Sample

The researcher used the universal sampling technique in each type of respondents classified as regular employees. The target respondents included in this study were the regular employees, male and female, aged 18 and above, with permanent status of employment from the rank and file, supervisors, and managers of the plastic manufacturing company which numbered to 200 employees. The researcher excluded all contractual and manual workers within the organization as well as those employees from other type of industries. The respondents' participation was voluntary in nature, meaning that those eligible to participate could withdraw at any time and discontinue participating without pressure, penalty or loss of benefits to which they would otherwise by no means however, all qualified respondents remained and did not terminate their participation. No reasons like fear of discrimination; feeling of coercion or intimidation; disbelief on the confidentiality and integrity of the study; become uncomfortable and discontent during the survey and interview; or simply a change of mind during the data collection and interpretation were manifested among the participants. The technique permits every population unit to have equal chances of being chosen (Singh, 2013). The sample was collected from the respondents were all workers thinking they would have a detailed and

thorough understanding of the human resource management practices being employed and their effect on the organization's organizational culture.

Fig. 2. The Philippine Map and Panabo, Davao del Norte

2.3 Research Instrument

For the researcher to achieve the objectives of this study, the modified survey questionnaires as research instrument were used in order to gather relevant information desired for this study. A modified survey questionnaire was designed to determine the level of human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company in Davao Region. The scholarly designed questionnaire was adapted from existing materials made and used by credible scholars and researchers on the topic under investigation and being studied. In this study, human resource management practices was measured using 50 items that include professional training, career management, and retention. The items were adapted from Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, and Mónico (2014). The response format was based on a five point Likert scale on culture which comprised of 24 items to clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture, and hierarchy culture. The items were adopted from Jones (2009). The response format was based on a five point Likert scale to indicate your level of agreement or disagreement. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis. The degree of responses by the respondents to parts I and II was measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The responses were categorized and interpreted as follows:

Part I. Human Resource Management Practices

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	very high	The items in the HRMP are always manifested.
3.40-4.19	high	The items in the HRMP are frequently manifested.
2.60-3.39	moderate	The items in the HRMP are sometimes manifested.
1.80-2.59	low	The items in the HRMP are seldom manifested.
1.00-1.79	very low	The items in the HRMP are never manifested.

Part II. Organizational Culture

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	very high	The items in the OC are always observed.
3.40-4.19	high	The items in the OC are frequently observed.
2.60-3.39	moderate	The items in the OC are sometimes observed.
1.80-2.59	low	The items in the OC are seldom observed.
1.00-1.79	very low	The items in the OC are never observed.

2.4 Data Collection

The data were gathered from various secondary sources, such as journals, dissertations, newspapers and the internet. The primary data were collected through a variables-related questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into three parts: the first contains items relating to the characteristics of the respondents. The second part consists of 50 Likert-type items pertaining to HRM practices and the third part consists of 24 Likert-type items pertaining to organizational culture. The researcher obtained the permission and approval from the general manager of the selected plastic manufacturing company through a formal letter of authorization. After the approval, the researcher has personally distributed and administer the research instrument to appropriate respondents. The questionnaire was pre-tested, and using Cronbach's Alpha, an internal accuracy was determined. The data gathered from the survey were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted statistically through the help of an expert who is proficient in the field of research.

2.5 Statistical Tools

The study used the following statistical tools to validate and develop reliable interpretation for hypothesis testing:

Mean. This was used to determine the level of human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees in selected plastic manufacturing companies in Davao Region.

The Pearson Product Moment Coefficient Correlation (Pearson r). This statistical analysis was used to assess the significance of the relationship between human resource management practices and employee organizational culture in selected Davao region plastic manufacturing companies.

Regression Analysis. This is a statistical technique used to investigate and model the relationship among variables. The important goal of regression analysis is to estimate the parameter unknown in the regression model. In order to establish causality, the relationship between regressor and the response must have a basis outside the sample data.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethics is a valuable imperative that is highly regarded in this paper. Thus, the researcher submitted the study to the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) to ensure that all ethical considerations in doing research are held and respected.

In this analysis, the researcher ethically established that participants should not be subjected to harm in any way whatsoever and priority was given to maintaining the integrity of participants in the research. Prior to the analysis, full consent was obtained from the respondents and the privacy protection of the research participants was ensured. All forms of communication were conducted with honesty and transparency in relation to the study. To tackle the ethical implications of this research paper effectively, the researcher maintained an adequate level of confidentiality of the study data and information on the following ethical issues as set out below:

Voluntary Participation. Insofar as data source is concerned, respondents' participation is voluntary in nature, devoid of fear and intimidation. After explaining to the potential respondent, the purpose and process of the study as well as his or her rights and responsibilities as study participant, the researcher allowed the respondent to decide based on his or her willingness to participate, without coercion, pressure and aggravation.

Privacy and Confidentiality. As with privacy and confidentiality, respondents were not obliged to write or disclose their real names on the questionnaire and on the interview profile sheet. They can use pen or code names instead to maintain privacy and anonymity. Moreover, the identity and personal details of the respondents were not revealed in any of the study's chapters. The data collection was done on the most convenient time and place of the respondents.

Informed Consent Process. All study participants went through an informed consent process where they were given a consent provision embedded on the survey questionnaire and on the interview guide. The respondents had affixed their signature to confirm their willingness to answer and be part of the study voluntarily. During the interview and focused group discussion, a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) was provided to remind the study participants and the researcher that all information shared and discovered are confidential and private.

Recruitment and Permission. Before the actual data collection, a "Request Letter to Conduct the Study" was presented to the General Manager of the company to ask consent in conducting the study especially in administering the survey and conducting the inquiry. After getting the approval, the researcher requested assistance from the plant superintendents of the organization to distribute and retrieve the filled-out instruments during their toolbox meeting, hence the required number of respondents was reached.

Transparency. The researcher safeguarded the proper implementation of the methods used in the study. In the spirit of honesty and transparency, the researcher educated study participants about the pros and cons of their participation. All the necessary documents that support data analysis were secured for reference and easy access by the readers. Through this, a better understanding of the study results is achieved. Further, the findings are discussed comprehensively especially the information that may have an implication in the interpretation and analysis of the results. Lastly, the

researcher described the extent of his involvement and how he held objectively in analyzing data and presenting the results.

Good Faith. The researcher also showed them the approved letter from the UM research committee to assure them that the study is conducted in good faith and solely for academic purposes. Likewise, the researcher oriented them about the mechanisms on accessing and safekeeping of all their information and answers to appease them of their confidentiality and privacy concerns. The researcher emphasized that she will not resort to deception and intimidation just to get things done and achieve the study objectives.

Benefit. Since active participation and commitment from the study participants is imperative to ensure that the study will achieve its objectives, the researcher informed the participants on the benefits that they can get as well as the contribution that they can provide to the profession. Through their responses and valuable inputs, they may have better understanding about the human resource management practices and organizational culture of the company. This may be instrumental to nurture in them that sense of engagement towards their work and their organization, thus improve the employee retention of the employees.

Risk. The researcher is aware of the possible risks or perils that the respondents may experience like they may feel pressured or uncomfortable in answering the instruments; anxious of the results which may be unfavorable to the profession to which they are identified with; and apprehensive about the secrecy and confidentiality of the information shared to the study. In this regard, the researcher exerted effort to earn the trust of the respondents through establishing rapport and connection with them.

Plagiarism. The researcher puts high regard to scholarly work and academic honesty, hence a plagiarism checker, the Turnitin software, was used to ensure that there will be no trace of misrepresentation of someone else's work. While borrowing key concepts and insights from experts is permissibly encouraged in research, the researcher did paraphrasing of lent claims and arguments without distorting or discrediting the source. A softcopy of the paper in Microsoft word format was uploaded in the software and see if all has been researcher's work already. As for the grammar, the researcher utilized the Grammarly software in order to correct errors in writing mechanics.

Fabrication and Falsification. Similarly, this research underwent a rigorous process to ensure that only reliable data is processed, and accurate interpretation and analysis is presented. The researcher did not make up the data, manipulated findings to favor personal biases, and generated conclusion without basis or that is not results-based. The study was entirely done in good faith, free from conflict of interest and falsification. There were no misrepresentation of models or theoretical expectations as all theories and propositions presented in the paper have legitimate authors and are properly cited which could be cross-checked in the references. Furthermore, five respected experts in the field of research checked the survey questionnaire and interview guide used as the primary tools for data collection.

Conflict of Interest. In retrospect, the basis of this study is a set of conditions under which a professional judgment about primary interest such as the well-being of the participants or the validity of the analysis appears to be affected by a secondary interest such as financial or academic benefits or recognitions. There is no conflict of interest in research when the researcher has interests in the results of the research that could contribute to a personal advantage and thus could compromise the integrity of the research in actuality or appearance.

Qualification. The researcher had recognized her limited exposure to the mixed methods approach. Consequently, she sought guidance and directions from her adviser, her mentors and panelists, as well as from her peers who are proficient in this method. Further, the researcher was closely working with her adviser to ensure proper implementation of the research protocols and ethics.

Authorship. Lastly, as with authorship, the researcher served as the primary author while the research adviser stood as the co-author. The adviser assisted the researcher to finish the study in a scholarly manner and through a rigorous process. The adviser helped in finding the appropriate theories, getting relevant literatures, making correct analysis and inferences and complying with research protocols and mechanics.

III. Results

Presented in this chapter are the data analyses of findings based on the data gathered. Discussions are arranged as follows: application level of human resource management practices, level of employee organizational culture, significant relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company and the domain of human resource management practices best influences the organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company. It can be noted that the standard deviation ranged from 0.20 to 0.95 within the typical standard deviation for a 5-point Likert scale means that the scores obtained in this sample are similar to the mean, suggesting a smaller variance in the responses of the respondent.

3.1 Level of Human Resource Management Practices

Presented in Table 1 are the responses of the respondents on their level human resource management practices which disclosed an overall mean score of 4.36 described as or very high suggesting that the majority of the items regarding human resource management practices are always manifested.

In addition, retention earned the maximum mean score of 4.41 or very good, based on the result while career management garnered the lowest mean score of 4.25 though still described as very high.

Table 1. Level of Human Resource Management Practices

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
professional training	.49	4.33	very high
career management	.47	4.25	very high
retention	.61	4.41	very high
Overall	.44	4.36	very high

3.2 Level of Organizational Culture of Employees

Illustrated in Table 2 are the responses of the respondents on their level of organizational culture of employees that registered an overall mean score of 4.37 described as very high level indicating that all indicators on organizational culture of employees are always observed.

Further, based on this result, clan culture posted the highest mean score of 4.48 or very high while adhocracy culture revealed to be the lowest mean score of 4.27 although still at very high level.

Table 2. Level of Organizational Culture of Employees

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
clan culture	.47	4.48	very high
adhocracy culture	.46	4.27	very high
market culture	.46	4.33	very high
hierarchy culture	.47	4.37	very high
Overall	.40	4.37	very high

3.3 Significance on the Relationship between Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Culture of Employees in Plastic Manufacturing Company

Presented in Table 3 are the results of the test of relationship between the variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had computed r-value of .607 with p-value of 0.000 which is significant at 0.05 level.

Doing a correlation among the measures of both variables, it can be gleaned that the human resource management practices and organization culture of employees revealed the computed r-values ranging -.062 to .572 with p-values 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. It implies the greater the value of the human resource management practices, the higher organizational culture of employees.

The results indicate the human resource management practices is significantly correlated with organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company. Furthermore, in their individual capacity, indicators of human resource management practices showed significant relationship with organizational culture as indicated by p-value<0.05 except professional training.

Table 3. Significance on the Relationship between Level of Human Resource Management Practices and Level of Organizational Culture

Human Resource Management Practices	Organizational Culture				
	Clan Culture	Adhocracy Culture	Market Culture	Hierarchy Culture	Overall
professional training	-.046 (.738)	-.189 (.167)	.030 (.827)	-.021 (.880)	-.062 (.653)
career management	.512 (.000)	.456 (.000)	.513 (.000)	.491 (.000)	.572 (.000)
retention	.532 (.000)	.381 (.000)	.499 (.000)	.443 (.000)	.530 (.000)
Overall	.570 (.000)	.471 (.000)	.546 (.000)	.519 (.000)	.607 (.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Furthermore, it was observed that all indicators of human resource management practices are attributable to organizational culture of employees. Indeed, the study results seemed to suggest that human resource management practices had a strong effect on their level of employee organizational culture. Such relationships indicated the researcher to further test the impact on human resource management practices of the above-mentioned organizational culture of the sphere of employees. Therefore, the method was used for regression analysis.

3.4 Significance on the Influence of Human Resource Management Practices to Organizational Culture of Employees in Plastic Manufacturing Company

As shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis of the influence of human resource management practices on organizational culture of employees. The regression model with three measures namely: professional training, career management, and retention yielded an overall F=40.54 and R2=.705 with probability value of 0.000 which is lesser than 0.05 significant level set of this study. Therefore, it can be stated that human resource management practices best influence the organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company. On the other hand, when taken individually, it showed that only retention influences organizational culture having a p-value of less than 0.05 level the highest standard beta coefficient of 0.552. This means that employees valued retention in the organization which greatly impacts its organizational culture of employees.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Influence of Human Resource Management Practices Best Influences the Organizational Culture

Human Resource Management Practices	Organizational Culture			
	B	Beta	t-test	Sig
professional training	.005	.005	.071	.944
career management	.086	.093	.690	.493
Retention	.552	.761	5.609	.000
R2	.705			
F	40.54			
P	0.000			

IV. Discussion

Discussions on the data collected and collated human resource management practices and workplace organizational culture in plastic manufacturing enterprise are discussed in this chapter. The discussion starts on indicator of human resource management practices which are followed by organizational culture. Furthermore, the findings of the correlation between indicators and the study of regression of the impact of human resource management practices and employee organizational culture are thoroughly discussed. Likewise, conclusions and recommendations derived from the results of the study are also conferred.

4.1 Level of Human Resource Management Practices

The level of human resource management practices is described as very high level in line for the very high level the respondents rating on professional training, career management, and retention indicating that the items measured manifested at all times. The employees' continuous development is greatly valued, professional training improves people's performance and carefully planned from survey needs to prepare, conduct and evaluate. Employee career management has concentrated on job security and stability and has well-defined succession plans, particularly in the absence situation, each employee knows which colleague to replace. Employees expect that hiring decisions are largely based on performance or merit, and dependent on skill development that allows the job to be retained. These include providing broad benefits such as life insurance, vehicle, health insurance, accident insurance, leave allowance, vacation pay, and employee dependent assistance. The organization has created programs that include promoting activities that involve employees to promote camaraderie and friendship, requiring both enhancing the physical work atmosphere and building more fun workplaces. Therefore, these activities are important if human resource management practices are to be held directly related to career selection, professional training experiences and retention (Figueiredo, Pais, Monteiro, & Mónico, 2014).

4.2 Level of Organizational Culture of Employees

The very high level of organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company is due to the respondents' very high rating on clan culture, adhocracy culture, market culture and hierarchy culture suggesting that the items measured manifested at all times. The company's leadership is commonly seen as exemplifying mentoring, encouraging, or nurturing. In my organization the management style is characterized by teamwork, agreement, and involvement. The glue holding my firm together is loyalty and mutual trust. Compliance with this business is running high. My company defines success on the basis of human resource development, collaboration, employee engagement and people concern.

The findings collaborated the study developed by Jones (2009) and it categorized organizations according to two dimensions. This concept presents four types of organizational culture such as clan, adhocracy, market, and hierarchy culture. Clan culture is a form of organizational culture that best describes as comfortable, cozy surroundings where engagement, communication and growth are the key values. Although, culture of adhocracy sets a dynamic, creative environment, creativity and agility are the key values. Whereas control emanates from person to individual, task team to task team, it depends on how the issue is handled. Organizations that have this philosophy try to produce creative results and learn new opportunities. The business culture, on the other hand, promotes a result-oriented atmosphere that maintains the core values like productivity and objective achievement. Competitiveness and efficiency are among the prime values for such companies of the business size. Nonetheless, the culture of hierarchy is hierarchical, and organized framework promotes efficiency and consistency as the key values.

4.3 Significance on the Relationship between the Level of Human Resource Management Practices and Level of Organizational Culture of Employees in Plastic Manufacturing Company

The overall test of the relationship between variables found to positively and significantly correlate between human resource management practices and organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Correspondingly, it has been denoted that literature concerning organizational culture owns predominantly confirmed its effect on organizational effectiveness. This meant that in comparison to relational models of human resource management, the idea of cultural sound and context-bound behaviors was important to argue on Universalist.

Human resources alignment with the organizational culture is a critical tool for the organization in achieving its objectives and producing results. Organizational culture can encourage its employees to join forces or engage in teamwork for change and improvement. Organizational culture support and HR strategy contribute to shaping factors such as entering success, efficiency, and whether human capital will ultimately be a core competency (Harrison & Bazy, 2017). Human resource management has a strong influence on the organizational culture in an enterprise which is an integrated strategic human resource management model. For example, the attraction of talented applicants will follow the organizational culture in the recruitment process, and the organizational culture will influence the recruitment processes (Williams, 2014).

An extraordinary finding in this research is that there is a positive relationship between HRM activities and the culture of organization. In fact, almost all HRM practices appear to align with aspects of the organizational culture. Earlier research into the relationship between organizational culture and HRM activities requires this relationship. As described in the organizational culture, selection, compensation establishment, performance evaluation have a significant effect on internal recruitment. This organizational culture has influence on HR activities and their efficacy according to them. This result has important implications with human resources administrators. They will employ the positive effects of organizational culture on these behaviors to excel in HRM activities. Conversely, undermining dominant aspects of HRM operations is possible for a society, if a negative culture exists in the company. When HR managers ignore the culture in the company, the positive effects expected from the HR practices can deteriorate.

4.4 Significance on the Influence of Human Resource Management Practices to Organizational Culture of Employees in Plastic Manufacturing Company

The research outcome showed and suggested a significant influence of human resource management practices on employee organizational culture in plastic manufacturing company as stated in the study's influence portion. And, the human resource management practices indicators retention obtained a very high level. This implied that retention significantly predicts the organizational culture of employees in plastic manufacturing company. However, it could be contingent also that retention of the variable human resource management practices best influences the organizational culture of employees due to its p-value. This means that employees treasured retention in the organization which greatly impacts its organizational culture of employees.

A significant body of literature signifying that HRM practices and organizational culture are related. McAfee, Glassman, and Honeycutt (2002) denote to the culture and HRM practices relationship as symbiotic that it operates to communicate organizational values and beliefs. As examined by Madanat and Khasawneh (2018), how the impact of HRM activities

on workplace satisfaction, pay equity, role creation by preparation and successful performance management effect the decision to retain employees and the commitment to a company based on higher learning.

V. Conclusion

In this portion, conclusions were drawn with considerations to the study's findings. The level of human resource management practices was very high level in all indicators manifested at all times which implied that employees valued professional training, career management, and retention in the organization. On the other hand, the level of organizational culture in a plastic manufacturing company was rated very high by the respondents. The results showed that staffare generally regarded as exemplifying mentoring, promoting, or fostering leadership in my company. Furthermore, the organization's management style is characterized by cooperation, agreement, and engagement. In addition, this gathered allegiance and mutual trust among the workers and the company. Therefore, the organization defines success based on human resource development, collaboration, employee engagement and people care.

In the sense of a plastic manufacturing company, the study found important relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture. Such results reinforced the study's assumption that aligning human resources with organizational culture is critical mechanism for the company in achieving its objectives and delivering outcomes. Organizational culture can encourage its workers to join forces or engage in collaboration for change and development.

Retention was identified to be the best predictor of organizational culture amongst the indicators of human resource management practices. Furthermore, it recognizes the impact of organizational culture and HR policy on issues such as performance, efficiency and whether human capital will unequivocally be a core competency (Harrison & Bazy, 2017).

Furthermore, the study result indicated that an important aspect is the corporate culture that drives the workers to leave the organization. Similarly, the research corroborated that managers will respect the organizational culture and its various elements, and try to find ways to enhance culture to attract more workers.

The study results developed alignment with that study's assumption that retention of workers is the capacity to retain employees within a company for a longer period of time. Retention of talent is important for businesses that move from start-up to fast growth. It is important to keep the best people nearest to the core competencies of the organization. Retaining workers is about circumventing the risk of attrition. Organization has to keep those people who deliver and have expertise and competencies that suit the key talent needs of the business (Haider, Rasli, Akhtar, & et. al., 2015).

The following suggestions are given in view of the above observations and conclusions. As the level of human resource management practices is very high and always manifest, the management may strengthen and continue to provide sufficient budget for professional training; enhance its succession planning especially on career management, and continue implementing improvements to increase retention rate.

Moreover, given that the very high level of organizational culture, managers may continue to value culture to retain more competent employees who provide value added services to customers essential for business continuity. However, since the results showed an important relationship between human resource management practices and organizational culture, the management may create and develop more organizational programs and activities that continuously improve the retention of employees in the organizations that deliberately and develop wilfully core cultural organizational components in relation to their HRM activities to encourage workers to engage in the society embraced and accepted by the management.

Finally, the researcher challenges those who are in the field of human resource management to strategically and innovatively design human resource programs since retention has been found to be the best predictor of organizational culture, it is suggested that management may enhance its initiated reward and benefit programs; design a more employee-friendly work environment to attract and retain employees; and to continuously innovate HR practices to match the emerging work attitudes and behavior of employees. Also, future researchers are also encouraged to read the study results for them to gain insight into how human resource management practices have a positive impact on the organizational culture of the plastics manufacturing company.

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